

THE ROLE OF APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN INCREASING PRODUCT COMPETITIVENESS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6371564>

T.S. Saidmuradova

Head teacher, Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry

R.F. Khalilova

Teacher, Yashnabod district 30th school

В данной статье рассмотрены вопросы об эффективности применения инновационных технологий в повышении конкурентоспособности товаров предприятий текстильной промышленности

In given article questions on efficiency of application of innovative technologies in increasing of competitiveness of the goods of the enterprises of the textile industry are considered

Today, special attention is paid to the development of light industry. The light industry is one of the most important industries in the world. In practice, the policy is to develop the export potential of light industry and create import-substituting production. We have enough opportunities to develop this network. For example, in Uzbekistan per capita per year is 230 kg of raw cotton. This is a very high figure, as these figures correspond to only 4 kg of raw cotton in China. However, even so, China's main foreign exchange earnings are in the textile and light industries.

It is known that at present most of our products are not able to compete with foreign goods in our domestic market.

Two main factors affect the competitiveness of a product. The first is a factor related to the price of the product, i.e. to achieve a reduction in production costs without compromising the quality of the product. The second is a factor related to the price of the product, i.e. improving its quality by giving the product new features that were not previously required.

In a market economy based on free competition, improving product quality is one of the key factors in increasing production efficiency. This is because in a market economy, the savings of social labor are mainly based on the consumption of quality products. The production of quality products will improve the technical and economic performance of manufacturing enterprises.

The low quality and non-competitiveness of the product is not an abstract category, but a clear reason that the enterprise is not viable. That is why the quality problem is now a strategic problem. The ability of an enterprise to achieve its goals, to ensure the competitiveness of its products, the order of its management and

organization is determined by the order of quality management. A quality management procedure is an agreed-upon approach to an enterprise that incorporates useful technical, management methods, provides the best and most convenient ways for people and machines to interact, and also provides cost savings for quality, data transfer [1].

In our opinion, the set of measures to improve the quality of textile products includes:

- Basic experiments and design work, as well as organizational and technical measures aimed at improving product quality;
- Measures to improve production equipment and technology;
- Requirements to suppliers to improve the quality of raw materials and supplies;
- Measures to improve product quality.

Improving the quality of products produced by enterprises in the textile industry will ensure the competitiveness of its products and, ultimately, the competitiveness of the enterprise. Competitiveness of a product is a set of characteristics that distinguish it from other similar goods in terms of the level of costs incurred to meet the specific needs of the consumer and its purchase and subsequent use.

Product competitiveness is the "ability" of consumers to distinguish between goods produced by the same enterprise, which have better consumer characteristics and technical and economic parameters than similar products of competing enterprises [1].

Competitiveness is observed in the market and the suitability of goods to consumer needs is compared and examined. Then the competitiveness of the product reflects the level of attractiveness for the buyer who is making a real purchase.

Qualitative and quantitative indicators of competitiveness:

- Competitive in terms of cost of raw materials, labor and energy resources;
- The positive position of Uzbek textile enterprises in the markets of neighboring countries (traditional business ties and long-term close cooperation), their competitive advantage is provided by a developed transport infrastructure.

At present, the products of the following textile enterprises can be considered competitive in foreign markets in terms of quality characteristics: yarn products, medium-quality coarse fabrics, down. Unfortunately, many other textile products today do not fully meet the requirements of foreign consumers in terms of their quality characteristics.

Modern technology automatically controls the linear density (thickness) of the products currently produced, simplifies the working conditions and ensures the safety of workers servicing machines using electronic devices. On new machines, windings and broken threads are replaced and connected using automatic machines. Maintenance of machines, their dusting is carried out using special devices. As a result, 98-100% of the products produced can meet high grades. Therefore, in our study, we

studied the impact of the use of new Ritter equipment on product quality and the impact of quality improvement on corporate profitability [2].

In our research, we calculated the cost-effectiveness of the existing spinning mill and the spinning mill, which is equipped with new equipment from Ritter, by improving the quality of products by equipping the production process with new technologies.

With the introduction of new technologies at the enterprise, production will increase by 133.2%. Net discounted income will increase by 125.5%. The volume of production of non-hazardous products is 16.6% less than at the existing enterprise with the introduction of new technologies. The payback period is almost 2.5 times shorter.

This means that if the company introduces new technology, the quality of the product will improve and 97-98% of the products will be of the first grade, and the economic performance will be high.

To ensure the required level of product quality, it is necessary to continue the "life" cycle of the product. "Life cycle" is the interdependence of the creation process and the gradual change of the state of products from the formation of initial requirements until its use or the end of the period of need.

The first level of the life cycle can be divided into the following stages: inspection and preparation (performance); preparation (production) and sale (payment) and circulation; exploitation.

It should be noted that the use of goods in accordance with the instructions may extend their useful life. The extension of the shelf life is as strong as the production of additional products. Thus, the rational operation of the product allows saving material and labor resources.

If the product quality is not at the required level, first, the number of interruptions on the crossings will increase and the useful working time of the machine will decrease, resulting in a decrease in its productivity. A decrease in machine productivity leads to a decrease in labor productivity, resulting in a reduction in the amount of output a worker produces per unit of time and an overspending of the wage bill.

On the other hand, the level of product quality leads to excessive use of raw materials. Deterioration of the use of raw materials leads to an increase in production costs, resulting in a decrease in the amount of profit earned by the enterprise from the sale of products, as well as a decrease in product and enterprise efficiency. This means that the financial performance of the enterprise deteriorates.

Third, the decline in product quality leads to a decrease in the use of existing equipment. As a result, the cost of repairing and maintaining machines per unit of output, as well as the amount of these costs for the enterprise will have a negative impact on the economic performance of the enterprise.

Ensuring that the quality of products is at the level of demand is a topical issue not only at the enterprise level, but also in the national economy.

LITERATURE:

- 1.F. Ergashev et al. Innovation management. Textbook -T : “Academy”, 2015.
2. T.Sh. Shogiyosov - Complex economic analysis. Textbook - T: "Science and Technology" 2012.